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Research Article

TO KNOW THE DETERMINANTS OF HEPATIC ENCEPHALOPATHY IN PATIENTS COMING TO JINNAH HOSPITAL AND THEIR CHILD-PUGH CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract:

Hepatic encephalopathy is the derangement in functioning of CNS due to compromised liver function resulting in a range of neuropsychiatry manifestations. Child Pugh classification is used to assess prognosis of liver disease mainly cirrhosis. Although previously used to predict mortality during surgery, it is now used to determine the prognosis as well as the required span of treatment and necessity of liver transplantation.

Objectives: To know the determinants of hepatic encephalopathy in patients coming to Jinnah hospital and their Child Pugh classification.

Place: Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Study Period: 3 months.

Subjects and Methods: A population based cross-sectional study was conducted. A total of 100 subjects were recruited in study. Selection was made on laid down criteria based on convenient sampling. Interviews were conducted through pretested proformas after taking due consent. Data was collected, compiled and analyzed through SPSS version 22. Demographic characteristics were defined using frequency tables, descriptive statistics were applied to determine mean, median, mode and standard deviation. Social determinants were shown graphically in the form of pie charts while clinical determinants were picturized in form of bar charts.

Results: Out of 100 subjects, hepatic encephalopathy was more prevalent in people above 30 years of age (97%), males (61%) were more commonly affected than females (39%). It was also found to be more in people with education below or equal to primary (71%), and those belonging to poor class (70%). 57% of patients had history of hepatitis C infection. Other important factors making up less than 30% include hepatitis B, UTIs, pneumonia, use of diuretics, anti-tuberculosis drugs, sedatives, type 1 diabetes. 74 % of patients were found to have constipation, 62% had history of vomiting 51% had Hemetemeses, 54% had melena. Vitamin B12 deficiency was present in 58% of those studied. 80% of patients consumed proteins (fish, meat) less than 3 times a week and 92% hadn't undergone any significant operation (Porto systemic shunting, appendisectomy). Only 23% presented with hypoglycaemia and 9% with hypokalemia. 64% of the patients had Child-pugh class C, 35% had class B and only 1% had class A

Keywords: *Hepatic encephalopathy, Child Pugh classification, cross-sectional study.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatic encephalopathy is defined as derangement in functioning of CNS due to compromised liver function resulting in a range of neuropsychiatry manifestations¹. Child Pugh classification is used to access prognosis of liver disease mainly cirrhosis. Although it was previously used to predict mortality during surgery, it is now used to determine the prognosis as well as the required span of treatment and necessity of liver transplantation².

According to a research conducted by Ferenci, in U.S., 15.5 million people suffer from liver disease and of these 73% progress to hepatic encephalopathy³. Study conducted by Devrajani BR, Shah SZ at a tertiary care hospital Jamshoro, Hyderabad showed that of different factors involved, infection was the most common in causing hepatic encephalopathy⁴. Other factors involved are constipation, GI bleeding⁵. Diabetes Mellitus, renal impairment and Hepatocellular carcinoma are the most common coexisting conditions with cirrhosis of liver⁶. Ammonia is the main notorious factor involved in pathogenesis of hepatic encephalopathy⁷. Most of the patients with chronic liver disease manifest Hepatitis B (22%) and Hepatitis C (28%) viral infection⁸. Hepatic encephalopathy is based on four grades and is basically a diagnosis of exclusion⁹. A study conducted in tertiary care hospital Hyderabad on hepatic encephalopathy showed that of the 87 patients of hepatic encephalopathy studied, 61% had low Hb levels, 78% had increase in leukocyte count, and 66 % had thrombocytopenia. Hyponatremia was there in 26 % patients and 33 % had hypokalemia¹⁰. Research conducted by University of Barcelona showed that male sex, increased serum bilirubin, potassium levels

and blood urea nitrogen and decreased serum albumin and prothrombin time are associated with poor prognosis¹¹. Endogenously present cytokines and benzodiazepines may also contribute to ammonia's key effect in brain i.e. swelling of astrocytes¹². Serum sodium level of less than 135mmol per L is associated with poor control of ascites and a higher chance of hepatic encephalopathy, hepatorenal syndrome and spontaneous bacterial peritonitis as compared to patients with normal serum sodium concentration¹³. Study at Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences showed that of the patients studied, most were in grade 3 (52%) And grade 4 (22%) of hepatic encephalopathy and other findings were: ascites (64%), Child' class C (62%), Hyponatremia (50%), low Hb (70%), Hepatitis C (62%) and high mortality rate (30%).¹⁴

As with the passing time incidence of liver disease and hepatic coma is on rise, the main objective of this study is to identify the various precipitating factors of hepatic encephalopathy and to assess their role in severity of disease according to child Pugh classification. This will also facilitate the medical workup of patients presenting with hepatic encephalopathy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross-sectional study was conducted in Lahore to determine the precipitating factors of hepatic encephalopathy in the patients coming to Jinnah hospital and to know their Chil-pugh classification.

Child Pugh classification was used to assess hepatic impairment that is an FDA recommended classification.

Child-Pugh score chart:2

Parameter	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3
Ascites	None	Slight	Moderate to severe
Serum bilirubin(mg/dl)	<2	2-3	>3
Albumin (gm/dl)	>3.5	2.8-3.5	<2.8
Prothrombin time (sec)	1-3	4-6	>6
Encephalopathy	None	Slight to moderate	Moderate to severe

The duration of study was 3 months. The study was carried out on the patients presenting with hepatic encephalopathy in all the medicine wards of Jinnah hospital in the respective time duration. Sampling of the population was done using convenient sampling approach. 100 patients were included in the study.

Sample size calculation was done using Epi info 2000. Pre-designed proformas were used for data collection and pretesting was done initially using 5% of population. The inclusion criteria consisted of patients presenting with hepatic encephalopathy while people with renal failure compromised exclusion criteria.

Consent was taken from all the patients and they were fully willing to participate in the study. Due care was taken to preserve their confidentiality and socio-cultural ethics were fully observed. Data analysis was done using SPSS version 22. The variables according to our study were defined as below:

Hepatic encephalopathy is defined as derangement in functioning of CNS due to compromised liver function resulting in a range of neuropsychiatry menefestations¹. Infections studied in this study include Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C 25 and Hepatitis D virus³⁰, also pneumonia, UTIs, bacterial peritonitis and meningitis 24, 36. Auto immune diseases include Grave's Disease, Inflammatory bowel disease, rheumatoid arthritis, thyroiditis, type 1 diabetes and ulcerative colitis³³. Constipation is no bowel movement in three days time²⁹. G.I.T bleeding includes upper or lower GI bleeding leading to decreased Hb level²⁷. Hypoalbuminemia is defined by albumin less than 2.8 gm /dl in accordance with Child-Pugh classification². Excessive dietary proteins include protein consumption in form meat, fish, poultry more than 3 times a week^{9,32}. Hypoglycemia is defined by glucose level less than 50mg/dl^{28,34}. Diuretics used include potassium sparing diuretics, thiazide diuretics, carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, loop diuretics²⁶. Other drugs include sedatives, anti tuberculosis drugs and antiepileptics³⁶. Surgeries include appendisectomy

and Porto systemic shunting³⁶. Hypokalemia is K level less than 3.5 mmol/l 35, 36. Vitamin B1 deficiency is manifested by: swelling, tingling in hands and feet, confusion, trouble breathing, nystagmus and memory problem³⁷. Alcohol intake was also studied³¹.

RESULTS:

Out of 100 subjects, hepatic encephalopathy was more prevalent in people above 30 years of age (97%), males (61%) were more commonly affected than females (39%). It was also found to be more in people with education below or equal to primary (71%), and those belonging to poor class (70%). 57% of patients had history of hepatitis C infection. Other important factors making up less than 30% includes hepatitis B, UTIs, pneumonia, use of diuretics, anti-tuberculosis drugs, sedatives, type 1 diabetes. 74 % of patients were found to have constipation, 62% had history of vomiting 51% had Hemetemesis, 54% had melena. Vitamin B12 deficiency was present in 58% of those studied. 80% of patients consumed proteins(fish, meat) less than 3 times a week and 92% hadn't undergone any significant operation (Porto systemic shunting ,appendisectomy). Only 23% presented with hypoglycaemia and 9% with hypokalemia. 64% of the patients had Child-pugh class C, 35% had class B and only 1% had class A.

Determinants	Frequency	Percent
AGE		
below 30 years	3	3
above 30 years	97	97
GENDER		
male	61	61
female	39	39
Total	100	100
OCCUPATION		
un employed	45	45
employed	55	55
Total	100	100
RESIDENCE		
rural area	15	15
urban area	85	85
Total	100	100
RELIGION		
non muslim	1	1

muslim	99	99
Total	100	100
EDUCATION		
below or equal to primary	72	72
above primary	28	28
Total	100	100
MARTIAL STATUS		
unmarried	3	3
married	97	97
Total	100	100
NO OF CHILDREN		
less than or equal to 5	45	45
more than 5	55	55
Total	100	100
SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS		
poor	70	70
middle class	29	29
upper class	1	1
Total	100	100
INFECTION WITH HEPATITIS B, C OR D VIRUS		
infection not present	14	14
infection with hepatitis B virus	28	28
infection with hepatitis C virus	57	57
hepatitis D virus	1	1
Total	100	100
ANY OTHER INFECTION		
no	60	60
pneumonia	13	13
urinary tract infection	18	18
bacterial peritonitis	7	7
meningitis	2	2
Total	100	100
CONSTIPATION		
absent	26	26
present	74	74
Total	100	100
HEMATEMESIS		
not present	49	49
present	51	51

Total	100	100
MELENA		
not present	46	46
present	54	54
Total	100	100
USE OF DIETARY PROTEINS		
less than 3 times a week	80	80
equal to or more than 3 times a week	20	20
Total	100	100
USE OF DRUGS		
not taken	59	59
sedatives	8	8
diuretics(potassium sparing diuretics, loop diuretics or thiazides)	20	20
antituberculosis drugs	11	11
antiepileptic drugs	2	2
Total	100	100
VOMITING		
not present	38	38
present	62	62
Total	100	100
APPENDISECTOMY OR PORTOSYSTEMIC SHUNTING		
not done	92	92
appendisectomy	4	4
portosystemic shunting	4	4
Total	100	100
LOW BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVEL		
blood glucose more than 50mg/dl	91	91
blood glucose less than 50mg/dl	9	9
Total	100	100
VITAMIN B1 DEFICIENCY		
not present	42	42
present	58	58
Total	100	100
HYPOKALEMIA		
not present	77	77

present	23	23
Total	100	100
ALCOHAL INTAKE		
not present	95	95
present	5	5
Total	100	100
AUTOIMMUNE DISEASES		
none present	76	76
grave's disease	1	1
inflammatory bowel disease	5	5
rheumatoid arthritis	8	8
thyroiditis	1	1
type 1 diabetes	9	9
Total	100	100
ASCITES		
none	13	13
slight	50	50
moderate to severe	37	37
Total	100	100
SERUM BILIRUBIN(MG/DL)		
less than 2	50	50
2-3	34	34
more than 3	16	16
Total	100	100
SERUM ALBUMIN(GM/DL)		
more than 3.5	29	29
2.8-3.5	50	50
less than 2.8	21	21
Total	100	100
PROTHROMBIN TIME(SEC)		
1-3	13	13
4-6	41	41
more than 6	46	46
Total	100	100
ENCEPHALOPATHY		
child pugh score 1	13	13
child pugh score 2	63	63
child pugh score 3	24	24
Total	100	100

DETERMINANTS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
CLASS A	1	1
CLASS B	35	35
CLASS C	64	64

gender of the respondent

socioeconomic status of the respondent

is there any history of infection with hepatitis B, C or D virus

is there any history of infection with hepatitis B, C or D virus

was the patient constipated(did not pass stools in 3 consecutive days)

was the patient constipated(did not pass stools in 3 consecutive days)

is there any history of hematemesis

is there any history of hematemesis

was there excessive use of dietary proteins(in form of meats,poultry and fish)

was there any vomiting

what is the state of presence and degree of encephalopathy

DISCUSSION:

Hepatic encephalopathy is characterized by the derangement in functioning of CNS due to compromised liver function resulting in a range of neuropsychiatry manifestations. Hepatic encephalopathy is on the rise nowadays and takes away a significant toll of patients so there was a need to identify various precipitating factors of the disease in our set up so that due steps and precautions can be taken by the people with impaired liver function to prevent progression to hepatic encephalopathy and also child-Pugh scoring would help the physicians to see prognosis of the disease and the need for liver transplantation.

In our study 61% of the patients were males, such gender difference was also obtained by research conducted at a tertiary care hospital Hyderabad (75% males)¹⁰. Also study at University of Barcelona had predominating male gender¹¹. 97% of people studied by us were above 30 years of age, study conducted at a Jamshoro hospital had same result where 67% were more than 40 years old¹⁰. 57% of the patients studied had hepatitis C and 28% had hepatitis B while a study published in Pak J Med Sci showed 28% to suffer from hepatitis C and 22% to suffer from hepatitis B⁸ and study at Pak Institute of Medical Sciences showed 62% to suffer from hepatitis C¹⁴.

Similar outcome was obtained by Mumtaz K; he found 70% to suffer from hepatitis C infection¹⁵. So, in our setup major precipitating factor is Hepatitis C infection that is quite common and is main cause of liver cirrhosis in our society while in Western culture, alcoholism is the main cause of liver cirrhosis²¹. This is in contrast to our study where 95% consumed no alcohol. 74% of our patients presented with constipation similar to study conducted by Basri R that showed that constipation is the major factor leading to hepatic encephalopathy⁵. Amongst the infections, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) was found in 8(16%) patients, urinary tract infection (UTI) in 2(4%) patients in a study by Iqbal et al¹⁶. This is similar to our study where 7% had bacterial peritonitis and 18% had UTI.

Main precipitating factors of hepatic encephalopathy include electrolyte disturbances, bleeding, infections, high protein intake, diuretics and sedatives¹⁹. According to our results, 51% had hematemesis and 54% had melena, this also is supported by results obtained from study undertaken by Dileep Kumar¹⁰ where 45% had GIT bleed and results obtained by Basri R had similar outcome⁵. A study conducted by Saira Afzal showed 13% of male patients and 25% of female patients to suffer from GIT bleeding¹⁷. 62% of our patients had history of vomiting leading to

dehydration that precipitates Hepatic encephalopathy 1 .Only 20% of our patients consumed excessive proteins. The findings of Dileep Kumar also had only 26% of patients with excessive protein intake¹⁰. Intekhab Alam reported that his findings consisted of only 4% of the patients with excessive protein intake 16 . However study by Atif had significant proportion (47%) of the patients that consumed excessive proteins¹⁸. We found that 59% of the patients consumed no drugs while 20% used diuretics and sedatives were used by 8%. Research published in JMPA showed following results: sedatives 6%, diuretics 21%. 91% Of our patients had no history of hypoglycaemia. This is matching to a study where 23% had hypoglycemia¹⁰.

Hepatic encephalopathy is also triggered by renal and electrolyte disturbances like renal failure, hypokalemia, metabolic alkalosis and dehydration 1 .In our study, no history of hypokalemia was found in 77% of the patients studied while another study in JMPA showed that 33% had hypokalemia¹⁰. Increased potassium levels are associated with poor prognosis¹¹. Various factors like ammonia, electrolyte imbalances may aggravate edema of glia; this explains the episodes of hepatic encephalopathy precipitation by a variety of unrelated factors 20 . In the end stage liver failure, deficiencies of water-soluble vitamins is quite common esp. vitamin B complex 22 . Similarly in our study, 58% had vitamin B12 deficiency. 37% of our patients had moderate to severe ascites while 50% had slight ascites. 64% of those studied had ascites in a study at Ayub Medical College Abbottabad¹⁴.

CONCLUSION:

Our study showed that most patients with hepatic encephalopathy were males, more than 30 years old, employed, dwellers of urban areas and belonged to poor class group. Most important determinants are Infections with hepatitis C and B virus, constipation, GIT bleeding, vomiting. Others include infections with pneumonia, bacterial peritonitis, diuretics intake and autoimmune diseases.

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Serum bilirubin (mg/dl) more than 3 was present in only 16% of patients while 50% had value below 2. Study at University of Barcelona has showed that increased serum bilirubin is associated with poor prognosis¹¹. Our result showed that 50% of the patients had serum albumin (gm/dl) between 2.8-3.5 and 29% had level more than 3.5. 59% of the subjects had hypoalbuminemia in Dileep Kumar's study¹⁰.It is proposed that decreased serum level of albumin leads to worse prognosis¹¹. Low albumin level and thrombocytopenia is suggestive of advanced liver cirrhosis. Prothrombin time (sec) was more than 6 in 46% of our patients and 41% had values 4-6. The coagulation profile was more than 5 sec in 54% of patients in a study at Hyderabad¹⁰. 64% of the patients had Child-pugh class C, 35% had class B and only 1% had class A in our study while of the expired patients at Jamshoro, 16 had class C and 4 had class B¹⁰. Significant contributory operations like appendisectomy and Porto systemic shunting were done on only 8% of our patients making them less contributory factors. Significant surgery contributing to hepatic encephalopathy was present in 2.3% of patients in study by Imran Ahmad et al 23 .

Hepatic encephalopathy is characterized by a large number of precipitating factors and some of these are potentially reversible. So, with proper management we can prevent the occurrence of hepatic encephalopathy. However, those who have liver diseases of chronic nature, they are prone to more attacks of encephalopathy in future. Considering this, our goal should be to define and identify the precipitating factors to prevent such occurrences and to raise the awareness among people to protect themselves from the potential causes.

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